

INFLUENCE OF THE FIBRE WINDING FACTORS ON THE PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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INTRODUCTION

The plastic composite materials are light and have the high tensile strength and elastic coefficient.

Therefore, they are effectively used to make the machines, equipments structures and apparatuses requiring the great strength and elastic coefficient as in the airplane, super high speed centrifuge and equipment for the space flight.

Now various methods to make the plastic composite material reinforced by carbon fibre have been studied.

The method of wet fibre winding is one of those methods which is used very much lately.

Many data on the property and use of the epoxy composite material reinforced by carbon fibre are well known.

But, studied data on the influence of wet fibre winding process factors on the content of carbon fibres and the property of composite material are known a little and have remarkable difference in these.

1. Materials used in experiment and their properties.

The property of high strength carbon fibre is as follows.

Diam. of fib	Numb. of fib piece	Density G/CM	Tensile str MPA	Elast. Coeff. 1E+04 MPA	Thermal Orient. of Fibre Len	Exp. Coeff. of Orient, of
M						Close
7	3000	1.7	3290	22.92	-0.35	5.5

The matrix resin of composite material is epoxy whose initial property is as follows.

Molec. Weight	Equiva- lent of epoxy	Density G/CM	Viscosity (50'C) E	colour
350	190	1.14	18.4	COLORLESS

Hexa-hydro plalic anhydride (HHPA) was used for high temperature hardening substance of the epoxy and alpha pikolin was added to speed up the hardening reaction.

To determine the mixture ratio of the spoxy and HHPA and hardening condition, we had added the HHPA by 70,80,90. Portion to 100 portion epoxy and analyzed the change of infrared spectrum absorption during hardening process.

To it was added the alpna picolin by 0.8 portion.

During hardening reaction the variation of HHPA is most considerable in 1850CM and 1785CM.

However, it is difficult to keep constantly the thickness of specimen. Therefore we have examined the change of 1850 CM and 1785CM with respect to 1610CM of epoxy that does not change during hardening process.

Assuming the intensity before reaction to be 100% and measuring the change intensity according to hardening times, then the decreased amount of HHPA can be obtained. The amount of NNPA after reaction is calculated by following formular.

$$G = \frac{(D_{1850}/D_{1610})}{(D_{1850}/D_{1610})} * 100 \%$$

where D_{1850} , D_{1610} -intensity of spectrum at 1850 and 1610 CM

o, t -time before reaction and of hardening reaction respectively.

The result calculated on the basis of analysis of absorbed infrared spectrum is shown in Fig.1.

As we can see in Fig.1 the addition rate of NNPA is very good at 70 to 80 portion. The temperature and time of hardening reaction were 160'C and 5 hours respectively.

When it is gone through hardening treatment at 160'C during 5 hours after treatment at 80'C, 2 hours, the property of epoxy, which the proportion of epoxy, HHPA and ALPHA PIKOLIN is 100:80:0.8, is as follows.

Density G/CM	T C	Tensile STR MPA	Elast. Coeff. MPA	Thermal Exp. Coeff. 1E-06, 1/'C
1.17	129	48	3200	67

2. Influence of factors of fibre winding on the content of carbon fibre of composite material and its properties.

The basic factors of the wet fibre winding to make epoxy composite material reinforced by the carbon fibre are the heating temperature of mandrel. Infiltration temperature of epoxy and time, tension of fibre and pressure of fibre winding.

Above mentioned factors change the properties and contents of carbon fibre of the composite material.

2.1. Heating temperature of mandrel

If the mandrel to wind the carbon fibre is not preheated. Epoxy is cooled down and its viscosity increases.

When viscosity of epoxy increases, the composite material cannot be manufactured.

Therefore, the amount of epoxy in composite material increases up, and then the strength of material decreases.

To examine the heating temperature of mandrel we heated mandrel from 50 to 100°C and winded the carbon fibre. In this the epoxy was impregnated on the preheated mandrel.

In this, the pressure exerted in the mandrel was 4 MPA.

The time of the penetradition of epoxy into the carbon fibre was 2 seconds.

After winding of fibre, the formed body was hardened at 80°C. during 2 hours and at 160°C during 5 hours.

The influence of heating temperature of the mandrel on the carbon fibre amount in the composite material is presented below.

Heat. temp. of mandrel 'C	Temp. of penetr. 'C	Time of Penetr. S	Pressure Of winding MPA	Content of carbon V L %
50-60	85	2	4	47
70-80	85	2	4	52
90-100	85	2	4	52

As we can see in the bable, heating the mandrel from 70 to 80°C was very adequate.

2.2 Penetration temperature

The epoxy resin is well penetrated into gaps between the carbon fibres and it results increasing of adhesive force of fibres, only if the viscosity of epoxy is low.

To decrease the viscosity of epoxy the penetration temperature must be increased.

We mixed sufficiently the epoxy of 100 portion, the HHPA of 80 portion and the alpha pikolin 0.8 portion and measured the viscosity of mixture at 50 to 90°C

The measurement result is as follows.

Temperature 'C	50	60	70	80	90
Viscosity of Mix. 'E	18.3	7.9	6.5	5.7	2.9

As we see above, the epoxy viscosity above 80 C is decreased lower than 6 E and the epoxy was well penetrated into fibres.

In the penetration temperature from 70 C to 90°C the carbon fibres were winded on the heated mandrel.

Here, the penetration time of epoxy was 2 S and the formation pressure was not exerted.

In the case that epoxy composite material was preminary hardened during 2 hours at 80°C and completely hardened during 5 hours at 160°C. The properties of composite material very according to the penetration temperature as Fig.2.

When the temperature is above 90°C, the gas discharge is active.

Therefore, the working circumstance is contaminated by harmful gases and winding work was difficult. As result, the penetration temperature of epoxy resin must be between 80 to 85'C.

2.3. Time for the penetration

Only when the epoxy is completely penetrated into carbon fibres, adhesion of fibres came to be good and the strength of composite material, too.

Therefore, it is important to determine correctly the penetration time. The penetrated amount of epoxy and the properties of composite material according to penetration time of epoxy are equal to Fig.3.

As can be seen in Fig.3, it was very good to keep the penetration time by 1 to 2.S

If the penetration time is shorter than this one, the complete penetration of the epoxy into fibres is impossible and the adhesion become bad. Resultly, the shear strength in layers of fibres of composite material is decreased.

2.4 The tension of carbon fibres.

If the tension applies on the fibres, the strengthening effect increases. In this, the fibres are ordered compactly and tightly. When it was winded with the tension on the mandrel, the amount of fibres and properties of composite material are equal to table.

Tension of fibres MPA	V %	Density G/CM	Tensile STR MPA	Shear STR. MPA
-	34	1.34	950	35
8.3	49	1.40	1100	45
16.3	52	1.42	1180	45
24.9	52	1.42	1050	40

The addition ratio of epoxy and HHPA, thermo-treatment condition is as mentioned above.

The penetration time and temperature of epoxy were equal to 2 s and 85'C respectively.

In this, the pressure of winding formation was not applied. As we see in experimental result, it is good to give the tension by 8.3 to 16.6 MPA.

If the tension increases above it, the fibres are broken and the strength decreases.

2.5 The pressure for winding formation.

The carbon fibres have the high elasticity.

Therefore, when they are winded on the mandrel, it is good to apply the pressure, because of the best adhesion of fibres layers and the increase of the amount of fibre.

If the pressure acts by 2 to 10 MPA on the fibres, when the carbon fibres are winded, that is penetrated by the epoxy during 2 s at 85'C, on the mandrel, the composite material that possesses the properties, as we can see in Fig.4, is obtained.

The hardening treatment of composite material have been done as above.

2.6. Influence of content of the carbon fibre on the properties of composite material.

According to the complex rule of composite material reinforced by the fibres the strength of composite material is proportional to fibre content.

By our study, the relation between the content of carbon fibre and the properties of composite material are equal to Fig.5.

The experimental value has the difference from the value calculated by complex rule.

This difference is made by careless handling of fibre and incorrect observation of the process of winding formation.

In other part, this means that it is difficult to realize ideally the complex effect because of the other process factors.

CONCLUSION

1. In order to harden the epoxy resin which has epoxy equivalent 190, it is adequate to add HHPA of 70-80 portions and ALPHA PIKOLIN of 0.8 portion.
2. It is suitable that hardening temperature of epoxy resin is taken by 160 C and hardening time nearly 4-6 hours.
3. It is advisable that the preheating temperature of mandrel of fibre winding is selected as 70-80 C and the penetration temperature of resin as 80-85 C. In temperature higher than it much gases are released.
4. It is sufficient for penetration time of epoxy resin into carbon fibre to be 1 to 2 seconds at 70-90 C.
5. Recommended tension and pressure of winding formation are 8.3-16.6 MPA and 6-8 MPA respectively.

LITERATURE

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Fig. 1

Photo. Strength of spectrum.

Fig.2

Fig.3

Fig.4

Fig.5